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General methods

Chromatography: Merck silica gel type 9385 230-400 mesh or Merck Al₂O₃ 90 active neutral, TLC: Merck silica gel 60, 0.25 mm or Al₂O₃ 60 F₂₅₄ neutral. Components were visualized by UV, Ninhydrin or I₂ staining. Progress of the reactions was determined by GC-MS (GC: HP 6890, MS: HP 5973) with an HP012 column (Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, CA). Mass spectra were recorded on an AEI-MS-902 mass spectrometer (EI+) or a LTQ Orbitrap XL (ESI+). Conversions were determined by GC-FID (GC: HP 6890) with an HP-5 column (Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, CA). GC-MS and GC-FID analysis method: 60 °C 5 min, 180 °C 5 min (10 °C/min), 260 °C 5 min (10 °C/min). ¹H- and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian AMX400 (400 and 100.59 MHz, respectively) using CDCl₃, CD₃OD, or CD₂Cl₂ as solvent. Chemical shift values are reported in ppm with the solvent resonance as the internal standard (CDCl₃: 7.26 for ¹H, 77.00 for ¹³C; CD₃OD: 3.31 for ¹H, 49.00 for ¹³C; CD₂Cl₂: 5.32 for ¹H, 53.84 for ¹³C). Data are reported as follows: chemical shifts, multiplicity (s = singlet, d = doublet, t = triplet, q = quartet, br. = broad, m = multiplet), coupling constants (Hz), and integration. All reactions were carried out under an Argon atmosphere using oven (110°C) dried glassware and using standard Schlenk techniques. THF and toluene were collected from a MBRAUN solvent purification system (MB SPS-800). Dioxane (99.5%, extra dry), dichloroethane (DCE, 99.8%, extra dry), N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF, 99.8%, extra dry) and acetonitrile (CH₃CN, 99.9%, extra dry) were purchased from Acros without further purification. Molecular sieves 4A were purchased from Acros, and heated in Schlenk under 180 °C in vacuo overnight for activation before using. All other reagents were purchased from Sigma or Acros in reagent or higher grade and were used without further purification. Complex **Cat 1** was synthesized according to literature procedures¹.

Representative procedures

General procedure: An oven-dried 20 ml Schlenk tube, equipped with stirring bar, was charged with amine (0.5 mmol, 1 equiv), alcohol (given amount), iron complex **Cat 1** (4 mol %), Me₃NO (8 mol %) and Toluene (solvent, 2 ml). The solid starting materials were added into the Schlenk tube under air, the Schlenk tube was subsequently connected to an argon line and a vacuum-argon exchange was performed three times. Liquid starting materials and solvent were charged under an argon stream. The Schlenk tube was capped and the mixture was rapidly stirred at room temperature for 1 minute, then was placed into a pre-heated oil bath at the appropriate temperature and stirred for a given time. The reaction mixture was cooled down to room temperature and concentrated *in vacuo*. The residue was purified by flash column chromatography to provide the pure amine product.

¹ T. N. Plank, J. L. Drake, D. K. Kim, T. W. Funk, *Adv. Synth. Catal.* **2012**, 354, 597 - 601.

Tables and details of experiments:

Table S1: Optimization of reaction conditions for synthesizing *N*-(4-dimethylamino-phenyl)-pyrrole (**3a**) from 4-(*N,N*-dimethylamino)-aniline (**1a**) and 1,4-diols (**2**).

Entry	2 [equiv.]	Solvent	T [°C]	Conv. 1a [%] ^a	Sele. 3a [%] ^a	Sele. 4a [%] ^a
1	2a / 1	Toluene	100	28	20	0
2	2a / 1	Toluene	110	73	71	0
3	2a / 1	THF	110	67	65	0
4	2a / 1	dioxane	110	70	68	0
5	2a / 1	CH ₃ CN	110	68	67	0
6	2a / 1	DMF	110	67	66	0
7	2a / 1	CMPE	110	71	69	0
8	2a / 1	Toluene	120	>99	96 (76)	0
9	2a / 1	Toluene	130	>99	99 (83)	0
10	2b / 1	Toluene	100	85	41	17
11	2b / 1	Toluene	110	94	44	21
12	2b / 1	CPME	110	90	25	26
13	2b / 1	Toluene	120	>99	63	21

General reaction conditions: General Procedure (see page S2), 0.5 mmol **1a**, 1 mmol **2**, 0.02 mmol **Cat 1**, 0.04 mmol Me₃NO, 2 ml solvent, 18 h, 100 - 130 °C, unless otherwise specified, isolated yields in parenthesis. ^aConversion and selectivities are based on GC-FID integrations.

Table S2: Direct synthesis of *N*-substituted pyrroles from anilines and 1,4-diols.

Entry	1	2	T [°C]	Conv. 1 [%] ^a	Sele. 3 [%] ^a
1	1b	R = 4-OMe	2a	120	3b 44
2	1b	R = 4-OMe	2a	130	3b 90 (80)
3	1c	R = 4-Me	2a	120	3c 19
4	1c	R = 4-Me	2a	130	3c 36
5	1c	R = 4-Me	2b	130	3c 90 (59)
6	1d	R = 4-F	2a	120	3d 16
7	1d	R = 4-F	2a	130	3d 30
8 ^b	1d	R = 4-F	2a	130	3d 17
9	1d	R = 4-F	2b	130	3d 75 (47)
10	1e	R = 4-Cl	2b	130	3e 63 (45)
11	1f	R = 4-Br	2b	130	3f 61 (44)

12	1g	R = 3,4-(Methylenedioxy)	2a	120	30	3g	20
13	1g	R = 3,4-(Methylenedioxy)	2a	130	51	3g	49
14 ^b	1g	R = 3,4-(Methylenedioxy)	2a	130	27	3g	24
15	1g	R = 3,4-(Methylenedioxy)	2b	130	>99	3g	68 (37)

General reaction conditions: General Procedure (see page S2), 0.5 mmol **1**, 1 mmol **2**, 0.02 mmol **Cat 1**, 0.04 mmol Me₃NO, 2 ml toluene, 18 h, 120 - 130 °C, unless otherwise specified, isolated yields in parenthesis. ^aConversion and selectivities are based on GC-FID integrations.

Table S3: Direct synthesis *N*-substituted pyrroles from aliphatic amines and 1,4-diols.

Entry	5	R	Conv. 5 [%] ^a	Sele. 6 [%] ^a
1	5a	R = H	>99	6a 90 (61)
2 ^b	/	/	/	6a (>95) ^c
3 ^d	/	/	>99 ^e	/
4	5b	R = 4-Cl	>99	6b 85 (57)
5	5c	R = 4-F	>99	6c 73 (52)
6	5d	R = 3-CF ₃	>99	6d 88 (55)
7	5e	R = 3-F-4-Cl	>99	6e 87 (65)
8	5f	R = 4-Me	>99	6f 87 (60)
9	5g	Piperonylamine	>99	6g 83 (55)
10	5h	3-Picolylamine	>99	6h 92 (76)
11	5i	Furfurylamine	>99	6i 71 (43)
12	5j	2-Phenylethylamine	>99	6j (41)
13	5k	Dodecylamine	>99	6k 86 (42)
14	5l	Cyclohexylamine	>99	6l 85 (33)

General reaction conditions: General Procedure (see page S2), 0.5 mmol **5**, 1 mmol **2**, 0.02 mmol **Cat 1**, 0.04 mmol Me₃NO, 2 ml toluene, 18 h, 130 °C, unless otherwise specified, isolated yields in parenthesis. ^aConversion and selectivities are based on GC-FID integrations. ^b**6a** was used as the substrate instead of **5a** and **2a**, no significant decomposition of **6a** was observed. ^cYield was determined based on GC-FID using decane as the internal standard. ^d**2a** was used as the only substrate. By the end of the reaction, insolubilized brown solid was observed. ^eThe conversion of **2a**.

Mechanistic considerations of pyrrole formation

Scheme S1: A summary of possible pathways of pyrrole formation from 2-butyne-1,4 diol and primary amines using bifunctional Fe complex Cat1 (upon activation with Me₃NO). Based on the mechanism proposed by Watanabe [Y. Tsuji, Y. Yokoyama, K.-T. Huh, Y. Watanabe. *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.* **1987**, *60*, 3456-3458] as well as [*Tetrahedron Lett.* **2007**, *48*, 5115-5120; *Tetrahedron* **2009**, *65*, 8981-8986]. Isomerization likely takes place by intermolecular transfer hydrogenation (alcohol dehydrogenation/C=C hydrogenation) but direct isomerization by other means cannot be excluded at this point.

Scheme S1: A schematic pathway to pyrrole formation from 2-butyne-1,4 diol and primary amines using bifunctional Fe complex Cat1 (upon activation with Me₃NO). The role of the catalyst is isomerization of the starting diols to the corresponding carbonyl compound which undergoes pyrrole formation. Based on ref [*Tetrahedron Lett.* **2007**, *48*, 5115-5120; *Tetrahedron* **2009**, *65*, 8981-8986]. The formation of succinaldehyde has not been detected.

Scheme S3: Chemical structures of catalyst precursor **Cat1**, **Cat1-O**, **Cat1-H** and the addition of Me_3NO to generate catalytically active **Cat 1-O** by liberation of CO_2 and Me_3N , **Cat 1-H** form is generated by reaction of **Cat1-O** with hydrogen gas or alcohols.

Alcohols to amines through
hydrogen borrowing

Scheme S4: Iron catalyzed direct alkylation of amines with alcohols through the hydrogen borrowing mechanism, previously established in our group [T. Yan, B. L. Feringa, K. Barta, *Nat. Commun.* **2014**, *5*, 5602].

GPC traces of selected reaction mixtures

Scheme S5: Control reaction of a typical experiment with 2-butyne-1,4-diol and benzylamine to form the corresponding pyrrole. The toluene solvent was removed, and the crude sample redissolved in THF and subjected to GPC analysis.

Scheme S5: Gel Permeation Chromatogram of the reaction shown above. Measurement performed in THF solvent. Data (whole graph): M_n (number-average molar mass): 260 g/mol, M_w (mass-average molar mass): 347 g/mol, D (polydispersity): 1.336; Molecular weight of the highest intensity of fraction $M_w = 100 - 200$ g/mol: 160; $M_w = 200 - 300$ g/mol: 215; $M_w = 300 - 5000$ g/mol: 340.

Scheme S6: Control reaction with 2-butyne-1,4-diol as the only substrate.

Scheme S6: Gel Permeation Chromatogram of the reaction shown above. Measurement performed in THF solvent. Data: M_n (number-average molar mass): 234 g/mol, M_w (mass-average molar mass): 284 g/mol, D (polydispersity): 1.215. Molecular weight of the highest intensity of fraction $M_w = 100 - 200$: 160; $M_w = 200 - 300$: 214; $M_w = 300 - 100$: 353.

Spectral data of isolated compounds

N-(4-dimethylphenyl)pyrrole (3a): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. 4-Dimethylamino aniline (0.068 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3a** (0.077 g, 83% yield). Brown solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 100:0 to 80:20). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.27 – 7.31 (m, 2H), 6.99 – 7.05 (m, 2H), 6.77 – 6.81 (m, 2H), 6.30 – 6.38 (m, 2H), 3.00 (s, 6H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 148.86, 131.18, 122.12, 119.68, 113.04, 109.27, 40.78. The physical data were identical in all respects to those previously reported.²

N-(4-Methoxyphenyl)pyrrole (3b): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. 4-Methoxy aniline (0.062 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3b** (0.070 g, 80% yield). Light yellow solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 100:0 to 95:5). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.29 – 7.37 (m, 2H), 6.99 – 7.06 (m, 2H), 6.91 – 6.99 (m, 2H), 6.30 – 6.38 (m, 2H), 3.84 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 157.60, 134.45, 122.13, 119.64, 114.57, 109.79, 55.51. The physical data were identical in all respects to those previously reported³

N-(4-Methylphenyl)pyrrole (3c): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. 4-Methyl aniline (0.054 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3c** (0.028 g, 36% yield with the use of **2a**; 0.047 g, 59% yield with the use of **2b**). Light yellow solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 100:0 to 95:5). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.29 – 7.37 (m, 2H), 7.19 – 7.29 (m, 2H), 7.04 – 7.14 (m, 2H), 6.32 – 6.42 (m, 2H), 2.41 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 138.44, 135.30, 129.98, 120.48, 119.33, 110.02, 20.80. The physical data were identical in all respects to those previously reported⁴

² J. C. Antilla, Baskin, M. Jeremy, T. E. Barder, S. L. Buchwald, *J. Org. Chem.*, **2004**, *69*, 5578 – 5587.

³ A. K. Verma, T. Kesharwani, J. Singh, V. Tandon, R. C. Larock, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2009**, *48*, 1138 – 1143.

⁴ Z.-L. Xu, H.-X. Li, Z.-G. Ren, W.-Y. Du, W.-C. Xu, J.-P. Lang, *Tetrahedron*, **2011**, *67*, 5282 – 5288.

N-(4-Fluoro-phenyl)-pyrrole (3d): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. 4-Fluoro aniline (0.056 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3d** (0.024 g, 30% yield with the use of **2a**; 0.038 g, 47% yields with use of **2b**). Light yellow oily liquid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 100:0 to 95:5). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.30 – 7.40 (m, 2H), 7.08 – 7.18 (m, 2H), 6.96 – 7.06 (m, 2H), 6.28 – 6.44 (m, 2H), 2.41 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 160.61 (d, *J* = 244.98 Hz), 137.15 (d, *J* = 2.86 Hz), 122.26 (d, *J* = 8.39 Hz), 119.60, 116.25 (d, *J* = 22.77 Hz), 110.42, . The physical data were identical in all respects to those previously reported⁵

N-(4-Chloro-phenyl)-pyrrole (3e): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. 4-Chloro aniline (0.064 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3e** (0.040 g, 45% yield). Light yellow solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 100:0 to 95:5). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.36 – 7.44 (m, 2H), 7.30 – 7.36 (m, 2H), 7.00 – 7.11 (m, 2H), 6.30 – 6.42 (m, 2H), 2.41 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 139.28, 131.00, 129.58, 121.57, 119.23, 110.79. The physical data were identical in all respects to those previously reported⁶

N-(4-Bromo-phenyl)-pyrrole (3f): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. 4-Bromo aniline (0.085 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3f** (0.048 g, 44% yield). Light yellow solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 100:0 to 95:5). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.50 – 7.60 (m, 2H), 7.22 – 7.35 (m, 2H), 7.00 – 7.12 (m, 2H), 6.30 – 6.45 (m, 2H), 2.41 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 139.73, 132.54, 121.88, 119.15, 118.65, 110.86. The physical data were identical in all respects to those previously reported⁷

⁵ T. Niwa, H. Ochiai, Y. Watanabe, T. Hosoya, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, **2015**, *137*, 14313 – 14318.

⁶ H.-C. Ma, X.-Z. Jiang *J. Org. Chem.*, **2007**, *72*, 8943 - 8946.

⁷ W. Chen, J. Wang, *Organometallics*, **2013**, *32*, 1958 – 1963.

***N*-(3,4-Methylenedioxy-phenyl)-pyrrole (3g)**: Synthesized according to **General procedure**. 3,4-(Methylenedioxy)aniline (0.069 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3g** (0.035 g, 37% yield). Light yellow solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 90:10 to 70:30). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 6.95 – 7.02 (m, 2H), 6.88 – 6.94 (m, 1H), 6.80 – 6.88 (m, 2H), 6.27 – 6.38 (m, 2H), 6.01 (s, 2H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 148.30, 145.62, 135.68, 119.82, 114.01, 109.93, 108.42, 103.01, 101.57, 77.00. HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for C₁₁H₁₀NO₂ [M+H]⁺: 188.07061; found: 188.07078.

***N*-(2-Methoxy-phenyl)-pyrrole (3h)**: Synthesized according to **General procedure**. 2-Methoxy aniline (0.062 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3h** (0.031 g, 36% yield with the use of **2b**). Light yellow liquid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 100:0 to 95:5). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.20 – 7.38 (m, 2H), 6.95 – 7.10 (m, 4H), 6.25 – 6.40 (m, 2H), 3.85 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 152.67, 130.21, 127.42, 125.72, 122.03, 120.85, 112.24, 108.72, 55.75. The physical data were identical in all respects to those previously reported: G. Pai, A. P. Chattopadhyay, Tetrahedron Letters, 2014, 55, 941–944.

***N*-(2-Methyl-phenyl)-pyrrole (3i)**: Synthesized according to **General procedure**. 2-Methyl aniline (0.054 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3i** (0.020 g, 25% yield with the use of **2b**). Light yellow liquid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 100:0 to 95:5). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.23 – 7.33 (m, 4H), 6.78 – 6.82 (m, 2H), 6.30 – 6.35 (m, 2H), 2.22 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 140.55, 133.79, 131.01, 127.45, 126.58, 126.49, 122.01, 108.64, 17.85. The physical data were identical in all respects to those previously reported: W. Chen, J. Wang, Organometallics, 2013, 32, 1958–1963.

N-(2-fluorophenyl)-pyrrole (3j): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. 2-fluoroaniline (0.056 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **3j** (0.012 g, 15% yield with the use of **2b**). Light yellow liquid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 100:0 to 95:5). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.35 – 7.45 (m, 1H), 7.16 – 7.29 (m, 3H), 7.02 – 7.08 (m, 2H), 6.30 – 6.40 (m, 2H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 154.47 (d, J = 249.3 Hz), 129.0 (d, J = 10.5 Hz), 127.11 (d, J = 7.7 Hz), 124.93 (d, J = 1.5 Hz), 124.73 (d, J = 3.8 Hz), 121.35 (d, J = 3.6 Hz), 117.03 (d, J = 20.6 Hz), 109.92. The physical data were identical in all respects to those previously reported: P. Wang, F.-P. Ma, Z.-H. Zhang, *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, 2014, 198, 259–262.

N-benzylpyrrole (6a): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Benzylamine (0.054 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **6a** (0.048 g, 61% yield). Light yellow oily liquid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 95:5 to 90:10). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.27 – 7.38 (m, 3H), 7.10 – 7.17 (m, 2H), 6.66 – 6.76 (m, 2H), 6.16 – 6.26 (m, 2H), 5.09 (s, 2H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 138.13, 128.67, 127.58, 126.94, 121.12, 108.45, 53.28. The physical data were identical in all respects to those previously reported.⁸

N-(4-Chlorobenzyl)pyrrole (6b): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. 4-Chlorobenzylamine (0.044 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **6b** (0.055 g, 57% yield). Light yellow oily liquid obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 95:5 to 90:10). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.27 – 7.40 (m, 3H), 7.10 – 7.13 (m, 2H), 6.64 – 6.78 (m, 2H), 6.16 – 6.30 (m, 2H), 5.05 (s, 2H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 136.65, 133.42, 128.81, 128.24, 121.02, 108.73, 52.57. The physical data were identical in all respects to those previously reported.⁹

⁸ G. A. Molander, D. W. Ryu, M. Hosseini-Sarvari, R. Devulapally, D. G. Seapy, *J. Org. Chem.*, **2013**, 78, 6648 – 6656.

⁹ I. Deb, D. J. Coiroa, D. Seidel, *Chem. Commun.*, **2011**, 47, 6473 – 6475.

N-(4-Fluoro-benzyl)-pyrrole (6c): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. 4-Fluoro benzylamine (0.063 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **6c** (0.046 g, 52% yield). Light yellow oily liquid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 95:5 to 90:10). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.07 – 7.15 (m, 3H), 6.96 – 7.06 (m, 2H), 6.65 – 6.75 (m, 2H), 6.17 – 6.27 (m, 2H), 5.05 (s, 2H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 162.22 (d, *J* = 245.87 Hz), 133.88 (d, *J* = 3.11 Hz), 128.65 (d, *J* = 8.11 Hz), 120.97, 115.55 (d, *J* = 21.74 Hz), 108.64, 52.58. The physical data were identical in all respects to those previously reported.¹⁰

N-(3-Trifluoromethyl-benzyl)-pyrrole (6d): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. 3-Trifluoromethyl benzylamine (0.088 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **6d** (0.062 g, 55% yield). Light yellow oily liquid obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 95:5 to 90:10). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.52 – 7.62 (m, 1H), 7.43 – 7.49 (m, 1H), 7.38 – 7.43 (m, 1H), 7.23 – 7.29 (m, 1H), 6.65 – 6.75 (m, 2H), 6.20 – 6.30 (m, 2H), 5.14 (s, 2H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 139.28, 131.09 (d, *J* = 22.29 Hz), 130.19 (d, *J* = 1.41 Hz), 129.30, 124.54 (quat, *J* = 3.84 Hz), 129.95 (d, *J* = 272.50 Hz), 123.64 (quat, *J* = 3.83 Hz), 121.12, 109.04, 52.81. HRMS (APCI+, *m/z*): calculated for C₁₂H₁₁F₃N [M+H]⁺: 226.08381; found: 226.08415.

N-(3-Fluoro-4-chloro-benzyl)-pyrrole (6e): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. 3-Fluoro-4-chloro benzylamine (0.080 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **6e** (0.068 g, 65% yield). Light yellow oily liquid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 95:5 to 90:10). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.13 – 7.21 (m, 1H), 7.05 – 7.13 (m, 1H), 6.93 – 7.02 (m, 1H), 6.63 – 6.73 (m, 2H), 6.18 – 6.28 (m, 2H), 5.03 (s, 2H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 157.49 (d, *J* = 248.78 Hz), 135.25 (d, *J* = 3.85 Hz), 129.08, 126.59 (d, *J* = 7.30 Hz), 121.28 (d, *J* = 17.87 Hz), 120.96, 116.76 (d, *J* = 21.31 Hz), 108.99, 52.10. HRMS (APCI+, *m/z*): calculated for C₁₁H₁₀ClFN [M+H]⁺: 210.04803; found: 210.04824.

¹⁰ Z. Zou, Z. Deng, X. Yu, M. Zhang, S. Zhao, T. Luo, X. Yin, H. Xu, W. Wang, *Sci. China Chem.* **2012**, *55*, 43 – 49.

N-(4-Methyl-benzyl)-pyrrole (6f): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. 4-Methyl benzylamine (0.061 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **6f** (0.052 g, 60% yield). Light yellow oily liquid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 95:5 to 90:10). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.13 – 7.22 (m, 2H), 7.03 – 7.10 (m, 2H), 6.66 – 6.76 (m, 2H), 6.16 – 6.26 (m, 2H), 5.06 (s, 2H), 2.37 (s, 2H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 137.29, 135.06, 129.32, 127.02, 121.01, 108.34, 53.07, 21.04. The physical data were identical in all respects to those previously reported.⁹

N-Piperonyl-pyrrole (6g): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Piperonylamine (0.076 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **6g** (0.056 g, 55% yield). Light yellow oily liquid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 90:10 to 60:40). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 6.74 – 6.79 (m, 1H), 6.66 – 6.72 (m, 2H), 6.63 – 6.66 (m, 1H), 6.60 – 6.63 (m, 1H), 6.16 – 6.22 (m, 2H), 5.94 (s, 2H), 4.97 (s, 2H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 148.00, 147.09, 131.88, 120.88, 120.48, 108.46, 108.23, 107.72, 101.07, 53.12. The physical data were identical in all respects to those previously reported.⁹

N-(3-Picolyl)-pyrrole (6h): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. 3-Picolylamine (0.054 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **6h** (0.060 g, 76% yield). Light yellow oily liquid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 80:20 to 40:60). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.40 – 8.60 (m, 2H), 7.32 – 7.40 (m, 1H), 7.20 – 7.29 (m, 1H), 6.62 – 6.74 (m, 2H), 6.15 – 6.25 (m, 2H), 5.09 (s, 2H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 149.05, 148.28, 134.66, 133.68, 123.68, 120.92, 109.02, 50.70. The physical data were identical in all respects to those previously reported.⁹

N-(2-Furfuryl)-pyrrole (6i): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Furfurylamine (0.049 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **6i** (0.032 g, 43% yield). Light yellow oily liquid was obtained

after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 80:20 to 40:60). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.32–7.42 (m, 1H), 6.68–6.76 (m, 2H), 6.30–6.38 (m, 1H), 6.22–6.30 (m, 1H), 6.15–6.22 (m, 2H), 5.03 (s, 2H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 150.74, 142.65, 120.67, 110.36, 108.50, 108.09, 46.05. The physical data were identical in all respects to those previously reported.⁹

N-(2-Phenylethyl)-pyrrole (6j): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. 2-Phenylethylamine (0.061 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **6j** (0.035 g, 41% yield). Light yellow oily liquid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 100:0 to 90:10). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.29–7.39 (m, 2H), 7.26–7.29 (m, 1H), 7.10–7.18 (m, 2H), 6.58–6.68 (m, 2H), 6.12–6.22 (m, 2H), 4.14 (t, *J* = 7.65 Hz, 2H), 3.09 (t, *J* = 7.61 Hz, 2H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 138.39, 128.62, 128.50, 126.55, 120.42, 107.95, 51.12, 38.35. The physical data were identical in all respects to those previously reported.¹¹

N-Dodecylpyrrole (6k): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Dodecylamine (0.093 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **6k** (0.050 g, 42% yield). Light yellow oily liquid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 100:0 to 90:10). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 6.62–6.70 (m, 2H), 6.12–6.18 (m, 2H), 3.87 (t, *J* = 7.20 Hz, 2H), 1.70–1.83 (m, 2H), 1.18–1.38 (m, 18H), 0.90 (t, *J* = 6.63 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 120.41, 107.71, 49.62, 31.90, 31.57, 29.61, 29.60, 29.55, 29.48, 29.32, 29.20, 26.76, 22.67, 14.10. The physical data were identical in all respects to those previously reported.¹²

N-Cyclohexylpyrrole (6l): Synthesized according to **General procedure**. Cyclohexylamine (0.050 g, 0.50 mmol) affords **6l** (0.025 g, 33% yield). Light yellow oily liquid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 100:0 to 90:10). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 6.70–6.78 (m, 2H), 6.10–6.18 (m, 2H), 3.75–3.87 (m, 2H), 2.05–2.15 (m, 2H), 1.82–1.94 (m, 2H), 1.56–1.69 (m, 2H), 1.33–1.48 (m, 2H), 1.19–1.32 (m, 2H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 118.39, 107.31, 58.65, 34.66, 25.72, 25.49. The physical data were identical in all respects to those previously reported.¹³

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3a

3b

3d

3e

3f

3g

3h

3i

3j

6a

6b

6c

6d

6e

6f

6g

6h

6i

6j

6k

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